

Physical education lessons in the process of unumpedagogik methods.

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***Anatatsiya:** the word constructive with the help of the teacher, the organizers of the business and the other side carries. Shuningdek, establish a mutual relationship with the students, will make contact with them. All full and clear picture of the word because it activates more of the education process in the formation of assistance, education function, active perception, and will help you to understand the depth.*

***Keywords:** order, story, report, thesis, word of the emotional task, assignment valuations, stimulate.*

Word of mastering the educational material with the help of the teacher the results of the analysis and, at the same time, the self-evaluation to promote the development of.

Thus, the physical education teacher of the word able to use the two tasks. As it is known, is characterized with the help of his reading the meaning of the materials used. The teacher of the student in relation to the emotional impact of the speech should be clear and understandable to the mood. This is a clear expression following the methodological recommendations.

1. The content of the learning objectives should be according to the word. For example, initially understand teach a new exercise, then the details can be while consists of images.

2. Using the words, it is necessary to emphasize the effectiveness of o'rganilanayotgan action. For example: to rope out than confident children tirmashib are possessed with the free method, although with difficulty master koordinatsiya complex actions. When I explained the excellence of the reliable style o'rganilanadigan however, that could change the negative attitude to him was.

3. Mutually relevant issues should help to identify some action in between the word business. The exercises carried out especially at the time of closing, it is important to forget. Their main benefit is in them and therefore less communication with a clear understanding of the emotional action is required.

4. The main strength of the word style at the time of use, the technical students understand the basics of physical exercise plays a big role. For this

purpose often separate words (“hands!”, “chief!” and others) tell them to stand out in the form of guidance for use.

5. The word should be imaginative. This will be more understandable to students, and that increases its visual. Readers are given the knowledge and driving experience, the teacher of the implementation of the adjustment depends on the goals that will gather the attention of those instances.

6. It is not worthwhile to carry on actions speak to the students automatically (except required to correct).

The meaning of the word in terms of function. Physical education problem in the yterms to take off on the basis of lies. Subject to terms and events related to oral defines the concepts. To help maintain this difference in understanding themselves familiar readers, the teacher received while the total words – understand terms allows. As a result, the short, but on the basis of a wide scope of meaning of words comes into the body of mutual understanding between teachers and pupils.

The emotional function of words. Teaching and educational tasks that will contribute to the solution of the word. With emotions when we say the word will strengthen the importance of, and this will help you figure out the meaning of them. The study shows the subject teachers readers through the same attitude. The interest for them to be healthy, confident that challenges, stimulates the desire to eliminate. The accuracy of the content emotionally distressed, logical and grammatical context on the construction of the sentence, obrazlilik of clear, pronunciation, imitation of gestures is achieved.

Using the word umumpedagogik from diverse styles into nearly all concerns.

Give conversation – xikoya statement form. Readers often by teachers of the game at the time of the organization of the activity is applied.

Imaging – method to form a picture on movements in children. Given a list of specific symptoms at the time of imaging of action. What you need to do, why it is said that you should do so, however, is shown. At the time of the initial idea of it at the time of the study due to the relatively simple actions are used. At this time the students can use their own knowledge and experience.

Explain. An important method for the development of a conscious relationship to move, because it is the main “for what?” to that question, the answer to the opening of the technical basis is aimed at.

Conversation. To describe their own opinion on the one hand, to strengthen the skills, active interaction help to increase if specific assessment of the teacher's work on the second hand, readers know will help. Look at the teacher questions

and student responses many times the conversation tab or view determine your country can be free.

Analysis. the same but different from chat it any assignments (e.g., games) are held after do. The analysis is one-sided it's just that the teacher holds two-way analysis of students participate in a conversation will view it. The second form of scientific and educational tasks more effectively allows it to take off.

Assignments. Put on the progress of the lesson before the lesson refers to personal tasks.

Evaluate. The result of analysis of the implementation of the action. Evaluation criteria related to the functions of the educational process. So this is a few type.

1. Growing evaluate the technique by comparing it take the reader to carry out other student exercise. Regular classes will serve to stimulate interest in this student.

2. By way of comparison exercise technical standard evaluation of an institution, this is the primary stage of education in the ability of readers to imitate the pattern options are limited in the time still applies.

3. Regulyativ determine by way of evaluation of the action, as usual, occupies the most part of didactic stable. Instructional exercise technique exercise it and comparing the results achieved with the leader individuallashtirish will force you to seek methods. However, such assessments only technically the efficiency of movement in physical education a critical evaluation of their understanding and performance of the state that could get better prepared for the students is good. Assessment criteria the teacher's approval or ma'qullamasligini reflecting "good", "right", "so", "bad", "wrong", "I", "feet higher", "bukilmas may", "could be bukilmas hands" and so on.k. as is characterized in diverse types of rebuke.

Teachers similar short-a short rebuke the basis of what they need.

Command – specific, and the word is from using the most common style in physical education. The performance of the action he immediately adjusting to its end, it may be appropriate to change the level of speed or action fulfilled and so on.k.

Perception of the visual style

This ensures that the perception of seeing and hearing o'rganiladigan style group action. The rhythm of action, see the level of speed, sometimes too demonstrates a comprehensive picture poses and more on action going to hear them in the future to restore the approximate basis expands.

The visual style of visual perception of the principle of nature is the main (but not only). With their help the reader the opportunity to live in the formation of

the moving image o'rganiladigan mushohada won. Currently that you need to take into account that the perception of seeing the same people, and the other is the perception of hearing in the better developed. Teacher education and the uses of style in the leading role of the possibility of individuallashtirish analizator should be provided. The group of the train at the time of perception it is necessary to use all the visual style.

Young readers often give good results of compliance to style shows. Especially, to work with children at the time of this technique is of great importance. Live in them, striving to follow the example, developed a strong ability to emulate. Shalong with it, this is not the same in different ages of children. For example, a small young intuition developed a strong perception.

The use of perception depends on the visual style of the level of education. In the initial stages of them cheats are frequently used. Improvement in the stage you will use to correct errors that arise from them.

All students who indicated to act only accessible to the visual perception of the learning style to deliver when and connecting them to be active only in the case of is impressive. The makers of liking this style otherwise, students will become the norm while passive mushohada. As a result, they may not only learn to analyze the movement of the child which is directed towards the outer side of and attention, decrease the activity of their mental processes, review a while yoqlama remains.

Action show

The teacher (or the teacher with the task of readers) of the display style of education is one of the most specific action. With the help of education on the basis of the display lies imitation. Conscious imitation of the actions of a student is determined by factors of a few willing to do

- 1) to analyze the ability to know see them in action;
- 2) the child's mental development should be renewable physiological compatibility with the complexity of optimal workout;
- 3) the knowledge level of the student on the action with the fullness that emulate you to imagine;
- 4) to emulate the self-control of quality control and timely availability.

Physical exercise to show some methodological requirements:

1. The use of the word kelmog'i should always fit with the style of the show.

The content of the show and the word on the ratio of on time distribution and the rate of application tasks and pedagogical tasks composed with the specific content of education should be defined.

2. Much of the content shall be binding in accordance with the objectives of education be show:

a) the first show, as usual, the standard technique should give a holistic picture do physical exercise. Being easy to restore it at the level of the students is carried out;

b) if it requires you to show that you can how to master the movement, then the implementation should reflect the high level of technical skills individuallashtirish provision of representing;

v) when the voltage that will be necessary to attract the attention of students and make for some action, just provision, these moments are noted; sometimes they show only part of the exhibition is not o'rganilanayotgan for more movement, the movement speed is reduced, the break in.

3. The teacher at the time of the show you need to take into account the aspirations of students in the emotional mode to emulate. Readers know that it is necessary to use the activity to increase.

4. Just a simple Oynali show, basically, it is desirable to umumrivojlantiruvchi used at the time of physical exercise.

Show visual educational kits

Visual aids the students with the help of the show action to be the subject of the image for additional perception creates opportunity.

Show some visual training every type of weapon - a should be conducted with methodological principles taken into account. It is difficult moments reflected in the poster to show in action. Therefore to describe the details necessary to make it free from their readers can distract from the main action. To check the results of visual perception, the teacher questions and student responses is useful. The posters show the single technical institution may not be required. Out of the tasks of education, in order to attract attention task during the lesson, students are certain poster or pre-hang to meet with them before you can put the next lesson.

Draw pictures with chalk on the device, if the teacher is able to perform them with enough skill, if it occupy a column of some posters in front of them, but full of accumulated exchange can't. First of all, describe some of the action items consistent, consequently, turn these items to the attention of readers attracted by the phase of the movement can create a picture on a consistent ministry. Secondly, the pictures chalg'itmaydigan the attention of the children, should be very simple. Third, such is pictures of the show in a very quick style. The teacher emotional impact to the reader the ability to draw a picture of the aesthetic and of great importance, also, with the participation of students completed the implementation

of the action imaginative displays them in a way to think, to motivate you to find their own mistakes.

The subject occupies less than the didactic possibilities of the application of the tools, however, it takes emotional impact on school age children especially small enough (e.g., the doll in the lesson – these are always interesting).

Show Kinofilm poses challenges in many technical, pedagogical, didactic creates a huge opportunities to show it during the process. Kinofilm action sports high-level implementation with the help of the qualification, as well as its different to get all of the details ilg'ab plains, and holistic case can be demonstrated many times in the large size. A rapid method, which is called the visual perception of image motion is of great importance. Thus, high-speed action is demonstrated. Image taken kinotasmadan proeksiyalar on the screen do not move with the speed of the film shows a lower speed than the case, this allows you to looking out at all of its details.

Sound and light alarm

Sound and light alarm to be hear and see the beginning and the end of the movement of the body brings into the necessary mo'ljali. Make certain the direction of rhythm and speed it up amplituda the level of the action.

Bayroqcha, the area of the pile in the soil of the characters, metronom shot and h.k. the signal is similar to simple methods like running and will determine the direction and height of the throw. The action is carried out to get information on electric nishan quick, elektrozvukoliderlar is being spread wide.

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